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144 Figure S1. Geographic and Pareto representation of studies included in the meta-analysis.

145

146 Figure S2. Funnel plot: prevalence by region.

Sex

Sex and Region

147 Figure S3. Funnel plot: distribution of sex by region.

Laterality

Laterality and Region

148 Figure S4. Funnel plot: laterality by region.

149 Figure S5. Funnel plot: morphological types by region.

150

151 Figure S6. Forest plot: distribution of sex by region.

152
153

Figure S7. Forest plot: lateralality by region.

154 **Appendix D:** Supplementary tables.

155 **Table S1:** Risk of bias assessment of studies included in the meta-analysis.

Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	Rating*	Risk
Ahmed et al. (2024)	2	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	1	0	2	75.0%	Moderate
Ahmmmed et al. (2020)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	1	0	2	65.0%	Moderate
Akay et al. (2020)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	1	1	2	75.0%	Moderate
Almeida et al. (2025)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	1	1	2	75.0%	Moderate
Al-Rawi et al. (2019)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	1	1	2	75.0%	Moderate
Al-Rumaih et al. (2016)	2	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	1	1	2	75.0%	Moderate
Anbiaee et al. (2019)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	1	1	2	70.0%	Moderate
Aslam et al. (2021)	1	1	1	N/A	0	N/A	1	1	2	2	0	2	55.0%	Moderate
Asmitha et al. (2025)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	1	1	2	70.0%	Moderate
Avsever et al. (2018)	1	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	1	2	85.0%	Low
Bandyopadhyay et al. (2015)	1	1	2	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	2	1	2	75.0%	Moderate
Berjjs et al. (2014)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	1	2	80.0%	Low
Bhandary & Kamath (2009)	1	1	2	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	1	0	2	65.0%	Moderate
Bolger et al. (1991)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	1	2	80.0%	Low
Bora et al. (2021)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	1	2	80.0%	Low
Capelli & Gatti (2016)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	1	2	80.0%	Low
Das & Sahoo (2016)	1	1	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	1	2	1	0	2	60.0%	Moderate
Djorić et al. (2022)	1	1	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	1	2	75.0%	Moderate
El-Anwar et al. (2020)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	1	2	80.0%	Low
El-Din et al. (2021)	1	2	1	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	1	2	80.0%	Low
Ghorbani et al. (2025)	1	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	1	2	1	2	80.0%	Low
Gruszka et al. (2022)	1	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	2	1	1	2	1	1	70.0%	Moderate
Jiang et al. (2024)	1	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	1	2	85.0%	Low
Kar & Altıntaş (2023)	1	1	1	N/A	2	N/A	2	1	2	2	1	2	75.0%	Moderate
Keleş et al. (2010)	1	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	2	1	1	2	1	2	75.0%	Moderate
Kucybała et al. (2017)	1	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	2	1	2	2	2	2	85.0%	Low
Nedelcu et al. (2024)	1	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	2	1	2	2	1	1	75.0%	Moderate
Reeti et al. (2020)	1	1	1	N/A	1	N/A	1	1	1	2	1	2	60.0%	Moderate
Shams et al. (2020)	1	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	2	1	2	2	1	2	80.0%	Low
Smith et al. (2010)	1	1	1	N/A	1	N/A	1	1	1	2	1	2	60.0%	Moderate
Stallman et al. (2004)	2	1	2	N/A	1	N/A	1	1	2	1	0	2	65.0%	Moderate
Uygur et al. (2003)	2	1	2	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	1	0	2	70.0%	Moderate
Vargas-Hernández et al. (2023)	2	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	0	0	2	70.0%	Moderate
Verma et al. (2025)	2	1	2	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	1	1	0	2	65.0%	Moderate
Yaprak et al. (2023)	2	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	2	2	2	2	2	2	95.0%	Low
Yigit et al. (2010)	1	2	1	N/A	2	N/A	2	1	2	2	1	2	80.0%	Low
Yousefi et al. (2022)	2	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	1	2	2	2	0	2	80.0%	Low

156 *. Evaluated on 12 criteria: (1) exhaustive literature review; (2) predefined inclusion/exclusion criteria; (3) explicit
157 assumptions; (4) psychometric scope; (5) adequate sample size; (6) follow-up; (7) detailed procedures; (8) standardized
158 measurements; (9) data per hypothesis; (10) statistical analyses with effect sizes; (11) statistical error reporting; (12)
159 valid conclusions with clinical recommendations. Scoring (0=absent; 1=incomplete; 2=complete; N/A=not applicable).
160 Overall risk (author-defined): low ≥80%; moderate 50–79%; high <50%.

161 **Table S2.** Contingency table for weighted Cohen's kappa agreement analysis.

		Rater 2			Total
		Low	Moderate	High	
Rater 1	Low	7	2	0	9
	Moderate	7	20	0	27
	High	0	1	0	1
Total		14	23	0	37

162

163 **Table S3.** Summary of studies included in the meta-analysis.

Study	Population	Sample	Study design	Methodology	Country
Ahmed et al. (2024)	Radiology dept(s).	111 (53 ♂, 58♀) 33.4±unkn years	Retrospective	CT scan (unkn, unkn)	Sudan
Ahmmed et al. (2020)	ENT dept.	135 (56 ♂, 79♀) 32.5±unkn years	Retrospective	CT scan (unkn, unkn)	Bangladesh
Akay et al. (2020)	Radiology database	204 (97 ♂, 107 ♀) 18–87 years	Retrospective	CBCT scan (coronal, unkn)	Turkey
Almeida et al. (2025)	Radiology clinic	120 (54 ♂, 66 ♀) 38.8±17.1 years	Cross-sectional	CBCT scan (coronal, 0.25 mm)	Brazil
Al-Rawi et al. (2019)	Al-Sharjah, UAE	106 (unkn ♂, unkn ♀) 39.2±15.6 years	Retrospective	CBCT scan (all planes, unkn)	UAE
Al-Rumaih et al. (2016)	ENT-Head/Neck Surgery dept.	121 (69 ♂, 52 ♀) 33.2±12.0 years	Retrospective	CT scan (all planes, 3 mm)	Saudi Arabia
Anbiaee et al. (2019)	Radiology archives	199 (159 ♂, 40♀) 31.7±13.9 years	Cross-sectional	CT scan (all planes, 2-5 mm)	Iran
Aslam et al. (2021)	ENT dept.	33 (14 ♂, 19 ♀) 12–75 years	Cross-sectional	CT scan (unkn, unkn)	Pakistan
Asmitha et al. (2025)	ENT, Head & Neck dept.	157 (107 ♂, 50♀) 32.9±4.3 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal, unkn)	India
Avsever et al. (2018)	Dentomaxillofacial Radiology dept.	691 (423 ♂, 268 ♀) 45 (5–84) years	Retrospective	CBCT scan (all planes, unkn)	Turkey
Bandyopadhyay et al. (2015)	North Bengal Medical Hospital	44 (unkn ♂, unkn ♀) ≥15 years	Cross-sectional	CT scan (coronal, 2-5 mm)	India
Berjis et al. (2014)	Isfahan forensic Medicine center	45 (unkn ♂, unkn ♀) 18–60 years	Cross-sectional	Cadaveric endocopy (Stammlberger's)	Iran
Bhandary & Kamath (2009)	ENT dept.	419 (240 ♂, 179♀) 11–68 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal, unkn)	India
Bolger et al. (1991)	USAF Medical Center	202 (109 ♂, 93♀) 37.1±unkn years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal, unkn)	United States
Bora et al. (2021)	ENT clinic	1,532 (825 ♂, 707♀) 33.7±14.5 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal, 5 mm)	Turkey
Capelli & Gatti (2016)	Rhinological Center	70 (34 ♂, 36 ♀) 45.7±15.5 years	Retrospective	CBCT scan (coronal & axial, unkn)	Italy
Das & Sahoo (2016)	Teaching hospital	339 (190 ♂, 149 ♀) unkn±unkn years	Retrospective	CT scan (all planes, 0.6 mm)	India
Djorić et al. (2022)	Clinical Center of Serbia	73 (29 ♂, 44 ♀) 59±16.6 years	Retrospective	Cadaveric (axial & coronal, 0.6 mm)	Serbia
El-Anwar et al. (2020)	ENT & Radiodx dept(s)	86 (32 ♂, 54 ♀) 31.7±10.5 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal & sagittal, 1.5 mm)	Egypt
El-Din et al. (2021)	Medical Imaging dept.	879 (540 ♂, 339 ♀) 34.5±10.7 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal & axial, 1.5 mm)	Saudi Arabia
Ghorbani et al. (2025)	CT imaging unit	1,646 (unkn ♂, unkn ♀) ≥18 years	Retrospective	CT scan (all planes, 1 mm)	Iran
Gruszka et al. (2022)	Poles & Cypriot Turks	715 (305 ♂, 410 ♀) 6–89 years	Retrospective	CBCT scan (all planes, 0.3 mm)	Cyprus
Jiang et al. (2024)	Head trauma admissions	384 (194 ♂, 190 ♀) 0.5–18 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal & axial, 0.5 mm)	United States
Kar & Altıntaş (2023)	ENT clinic	3,133 (1,599 ♂, 1,534 ♀) 57.2±unkn years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal & axial, unkn)	Turkey

Keleş et al. (2010)	ENT dept.	90 (62 ♂, 28♀) 32.4±12.0 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal, 5 mm)	Turkey
Kucybała et al. (2017)	Diagnostic Imaging dept.	214 (89 ♂, 125 ♀) 47.7±16.7 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal, 1 mm)	Poland
Nedelcu et al. (2024)	Clinical Rehab. hospital	106 (45 ♂, 61 ♀) 60.3±20.4 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal & axial, unkn)	Romania
Reeti et al. (2020)	Radiodiagnosis dept.	150 (79 ♂, 71♀) 46±unkn years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal & axial, unkn)	India
Shams et al. (2020)	Oral/Maxillofacial Radiology dept.	172 (75 ♂, 97 ♀) 10–70 years	Retrospective	CBCT scan (axial, unkn)	Iran
Smith et al. (2010)	School of Dentistry archives	883 (498 ♂, 385 ♀) 44.2±unkn years	Retrospective	CBCT scan (all planes, unkn)	United States
Stallman et al. (2004)	Radiology database	998 (400 ♂, 598 ♀) 0–98 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal & axial, 2.5-3 mm)	United States
Uygur et al. (2003)	ENT dept.	100 (71 ♂, 29♀) 32.6±13.8 years	Retrospective	CT scan (coronal, unkn)	Turkey
Vargas-Hernández et al. (2023)	Mexico General Hospital	142 (unkn ♂, unkn ♀) unkn±unkn years	Retrospective	CT scan (all planes, unkn)	Mexico
Verma et al. (2025)	Dental Records dept.	966 (unkn ♂, unkn ♀) unkn±unkn years	Retrospective	CBCT scan (coronal, unkn)	India
Yaprak et al. (2023)	University Hospital	200 (100 ♂, 100 ♀) 46±unkn years	Retrospective	CT scan (all planes, 0.6-1.5 mm)	Turkey
Yigit et al. (2010)	Radiology database	672 (480 ♂, 192♀) 31.5±unkn years	Retrospective	CT scan (unkn, unkn)	Turkey
Yousefi et al. (2022)	University Hospital	616 (247 ♂, 369 ♀) 44.0±19.4 years	Cross-sectional	MRI (coronal & sagittal, 5 mm)	Iran

164 CBCT (cone-beam computed tomography); CT (computed tomography); ENT (ear, nose, and throat); MRI (magnetic
165 resonance imaging); unkn (Unknown).

166 **Table S4.** Metadata of studies included in the prevalence meta-analysis.

Study	Country	Sample (n)	Cases
Ahmed et al. (2024)	Sudan	111	42
Ahmmmed et al. (2020)	Bangladesh	135	57
Akay et al. (2020)	Turkey	204	75
Almeida et al. (2025)	Brazil	120	24
Al-Rawi et al. (2019)	UAE	106	40
Al-Rumaih et al. (2016)	Saudi Arabia	121	67
Anbiaee et al. (2019)	Iran	199	29
Aslam et al. (2021)	Pakistan	33	6
Asmitha et al. (2025)	India	157	56
Avsever et al. (2018)	Turkey	691	101
Bandyopadhyay et al. (2015)	India	44	7
Berjis et al. (2014)	Iran	45	7
Bhandary & Kamath (2009)	India	419	169
Bolger et al. (1991)	United States	202	107
Bora et al. (2021)	Turkey	1,532	628
Capelli & Gatti (2016)	Italy	70	37
Das & Sahoo (2016)	India	339	5
Djorić et al. (2022)	Serbia	73	22
El-Anwar et al. (2020)	Egypt	86	44
El-Din et al. (2021)	Saudi Arabia	879	488
Ghorbani et al. (2025)	Iran	1,646	774
Gruszka et al. (2022) _ Cypriot Turks	Cypriot Turks	359	244
Gruszka et al. (2022) _ Poles	Poles	356	195
Jiang et al. (2024)	United States	384	153
Kar & Altıntaş (2023)	Turkey	3,133	1,402
Kucybała et al. (2017)	Poland	214	90
Nedelcu et al. (2024)	Romania	106	57
Reeti et al. (2020)	India	150	48
Shams et al. (2020)	Iran	172	52
Smith et al. (2010)	United States	883	596
Stallman et al. (2004)	United States	998	436
Vargas-Hernández et al. (2023)	Mexico	142	43
Verma et al. (2025)	India	966	546
Yaprak et al. (2023)	Turkey	200	84
Yigit et al. (2010)	Turkey	516	163
Yousefi et al. (2022)	Iran	616	94

168 **Table S5.** Metadata of studies included in the sex proportions meta-analysis.

Study	Country	Sex	Sample (n)	Cases
Al-Rawi et al. (2019)	UAE	Male	52	20
		Female	54	20
Anbiaee et al. (2019)	Iran	Male	159	22
		Female	40	7
Aslam et al. (2021)	Pakistan	Male	14	1
		Female	19	5
Avsever et al. (2018)	Turkey	Male	423	44
		Female	268	57
Bora et al. (2021)	Turkey	Male	825	361
		Female	707	267
Capelli & Gatti (2016)	Italy	Male	34	19
		Female	36	18
Das & Sahoo (2016)	India	Male	190	2
		Female	149	3
El-Din et al. (2021)	Saudi Arabia	Male	540	299
		Female	339	189
Gruszka et al. (2022) _ Cypriot Turks	Cypriot Turks	Male	170	112
		Female	189	132
Gruszka et al. (2022) _ Poles	Poles	Male	135	66
		Female	221	129
Jiang et al. (2024)	United States	Male	194	82
		Female	190	71
Kar & Altıntaş (2023)	Turkey	Male	1,599	675
		Female	1,534	727
Nedelcu et al. (2024)	Romania	Male	45	28
		Female	61	29
Reeti et al. (2020)	India	Male	79	21
		Female	71	27
Shams et al. (2020)	Iran	Male	75	19
		Female	97	33
Smith et al. (2010)	United States	Male	385	261
		Female	498	335

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170 **Table S6.** Metadata of studies included in the laterality meta-analysis.

Study	Country	Sample (n)	Cases	Unilateral	Bilateral
Ahmed et al. (2020)	Bangladesh	135	57	34	23
Al-Rawi et al. (2019)	UAE	106	40	22	18
Al-Rumaih et al. (2016)	Saudi Arabia	121	67	34	33
Aslam et al. (2021)	Pakistan	33	6	5	1
Asmitha et al. (2025)	India	157	56	31	25
Avsever et al. (2018)	Turkey	691	101	50	51
Bandyopadhyay et al. (2015)	India	44	7	4	3
Bhandary & Kamath (2009)	India	419	169	83	86
Capelli & Gatti (2016)	Italy	70	37	14	23
Das & Sahoo (2016)	India	339	5	3	2
Djorić et al. (2022)	Serbia	73	22	19	3
El-Din et al. (2021)	Saudi Arabia	879	488	217	271
Ghorbani et al. (2025)	Iran	1,646	774	630	144
Gruszka et al. (2022) _ Cypriot Turks	Cypriot Turks	359	244	98	146
Gruszka et al. (2022) _ Poles	Poles	356	195	82	113
Jiang et al. (2024)	United States	384	153	74	79
Kar & Altıntaş (2023)	Turkey	3,133	1,402	631	771
Keleş et al. (2010)	Turkey	90	90	61	29
Kucybała et al. (2017)	Poland	214	90	53	37
Nedelcu et al. (2024)	Romania	106	57	27	30
Shams et al. (2020)	Iran	172	52	32	20
Smith et al. (2010)	United States	883	596	224	372
Stallman et al. (2004)	United States	998	436	227	209
Vargas-Hernández et al. (2023)	Mexico	142	43	28	15
Yaprak et al. (2023)	Turkey	200	84	46	38
Yigit et al. (2010)	Turkey	516	163	94	69

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172 **Table S7.** Metadata of studies included in the morphological subtypes meta-analysis.

Study	Country	Sample (n)	Cases	Subtypes		
				Lamellar	Bulbous	Extensive
Asmitha et al. (2025)	India	157	56	28	17	11
Bolger et al. (1991)	United States	202	107	52	36	19
El-Din et al. (2021)	Saudi Arabia	879	488	212	61	215
Jiang et al. (2024)	United States	384	153	98	1	54
Kar & Altıntaş (2023)	Turkey	3,133	1,402	575	363	464
Keleş et al. (2010)	Turkey	90	90	7	20	63
Nedelcu et al. (2024)	Romania	106	57	24	15	18
Shams et al. (2020)	Iran	172	52	16	17	19
Vargas-Hernández et al. (2023)	Mexico	142	43	25	4	14

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174 **Table S8.** Metadata of studies in the CBPI meta-analysis of isolated versus combined concha bullosa.

Study	Country	Sample (n)	Isolated CB			CB w/ NSD		
			Cases	Mean	SD	Cases	Mean	SD
Asmitha et al. (2025)	India	157	17	16.40	3.93	39	17.18	1.39
Yigit et al. (2010)	Turkey	516	51	16.45	4.65	112	17.05	0.99

175 CB (concha bullosa); NSD (nasal septal deviation); SD (standard deviation).

176 **Table S9.** Metadata of studies in the CBPI meta-analysis of concha bullosa with septal deviation.

Study	Country	Sample (n)	Contralateral CB			Ipsilateral CB		
			Cases	Mean	SD	Cases	Mean	SD
Keleş et al. (2010)	Turkey	90	45	11.80	4.60	16	8.70	4.10
Uygur et al. (2003)	Turkey	100	29	5.10	2.40	27	3.80	2.00
Yigit et al. (2010)	Turkey	516	67	18.05	0.87	8	15.67	1.17

177 CB (concha bullosa); SD (standard deviation).